

PERSONALITY TRAITS AS PREDICTORS OF JOB PERFORMANCE AMONG NURSES IN PUBLIC HOSPITALS IN EDO STATE, NIGERIA

BY

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Abstract

The study examined personality traits as predictors of job performance among nurses in public hospitals in Edo State of Nigeria. The study determined the relationship between nurses' traits which include: openness to experience, conscientiousness, extroversion, agreeableness, neuroticism and job performance of nurses. The correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised of 320 nurses. Multistage stratified sampling random procedure was employed to sample 222 nurses from the 30 public hospitals in Edo State. This sample represents 40 percent of nurses from Central Hospital Benin City and 100% of nurses from other 30 public hospitals. A questionnaire titled: Personality Traits and Nurses' Job Performance Questionnaire (PTNPQ) was used for the study. The reliability indices of 0.75, 0.84, 0.73, 0.79, 0.81, 0.77 were obtained. The hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) technique and Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (MLRA) with case selection preference at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed that openness to experience, conscientiousness, extroversion and agreeableness showed significant positive relationship with job performance of nurses ($p < 0.05$). However, only neuroticism had a negative and insignificant relationship with job performance ($p > 0.05$). Based on the findings it was recommended that there should be professional development programs tailored to enhance nurses' big five personality traits in fostering a culture of innovation and adaptability within the workplace.

Keywords: Personality Traits, Openness to Experience, Conscientiousness, Extroversion, Agreeableness, Neuroticism, Job Performance, Nurses, Public Hospitals

Introduction

In the world of work, there are not many things that are as widely acknowledged as the notion of job performance. It is such a large and nebulous concept that many researchers have their own ideas of what it is and what it looks like. This has also been an issue in the field of industrial-organizational (I-O) psychology, where job performance has undergone more than a few conceptualizations over the years. Job performance is defined as the aggregate expected value derived from employees' behaviours over a specific time-frame (Campbell & Wiernik, 2015). Job performance encompasses both task performance and contextual performance (Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994, citing Borman & Motowidlo, 1993).

Motowidlo & Van Scotter (1994) differentiate between the two types of job performance: task performance and contextual performance. Task performance involves activities typically outlined in job descriptions, such as transforming materials into goods and services, including tasks like sales or operating manufacturing equipment. Contextual performance, on the other hand, refers to behaviours that enhance organizational effectiveness by influencing the psychological, social, and organizational context of work (Motowidlo & Van Scotter, 1994). Furthermore, affective domain can occur through its effect on other people, an individual's development of knowledge and skills, or affecting the organization's resources (Ong et al., 2020). Contextual performance also includes volunteering for additional assignments, persistence in completing difficult activities, working with others to assist in completion of their tasks,

and supporting organizational policies and objectives, even when it might be convenient (Ong et al., 2020). Both contextual and task performance can have a positive or negative effect on the organization. Our focus on this study is that of nurse's job performance.

Nursing job performance is characterized as the delivery of patient care that aligns with the nurse's professional competencies, encompassing a wide range of related activities and processes (Mahat et al., 2018). By enhancing their job performance, nurses can effectively adapt to the evolving healthcare landscape and meet the changing needs of patients by applying their expertise and knowledge (Lee & Park, 2022).

Researches to improve nursing job performance have proceeded locally and globally, and grit is attracting attention as an important concept that can successfully enhance nursing job performance (Choi, 2019). Grit is defined as perseverance and passion for long-term goals; moreover, it is the driving force for overcoming failure, adversity, and frustration in achieving long-term goals and is an important part of achieving goals and talent. High levels of job performance among nurses lead to increased productivity, enhanced service quality, and improved patient care. Conversely, suboptimal nursing job performance poses a significant risk to patient safety and care within hospitals settings (Zhang et al., 2023). For the purpose of this study the researcher intended to examine the following traits which are referred to as the big five personality traits which are: extroversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness to experience and neuroticism.

Extroversion is the ability of nurses in the hospitals to be energetic and not shy, enjoy being with other people in work place. These nurses are very friendly; they are concerned with things outside self that is with the external environment rather than with one's own thought and feelings (Judge & Zapata,

2015). Nurses with this type of trait are supposed to improve on their job performance because they can easily interact freely with the patients and non-patients in the hospitals.

Agreeableness has to do with the nurses that support one another in place of work; they render helping hands especially when co-nurse is absent or not punctual in place of work. Agreeableness nurses are ready to continue doing the job before her colleagues will eventually be showed up (Lin et al., 2021). It is necessary for nurses to agree with one another in order to achieve a common goal. Therefore, it is expected that nurses with this trait can carry out their job effectively thereby making job performance to be realized.

Nurses that have conscientiousness traits are goal oriented, they do not want to be last rather want to be "in time" before deadline (Holman & Hughes, 2021). These nurses want to be thorough in their place of work. It is expected that nurses that possess this trait can enhance job performance positively in their various hospitals.

Another personality trait that is needed for the effective job performance of nurses is openness to experience. Openness to experience has to do with nurses that are very inquisitive, aspiring to discover new strategies or rather new methods by which they can reach their goals (Hee et al., 2020). Nurses with this trait are always eager to learn something new, discovering the known to an unknown; it is expected that nurses with this traits can enhances job performance in their various hospitals (Holman & Hughes, 2021).

Neuroticism trait is associated with distress and dissatisfaction, it is the trait disposition to experience negative affects including anger and anxiety, self-conscientiousness, irritability and emotional. Nurses that have this trait can easily get upset, unable to handle stress well thereby given room to

depression (Judge & Zapata, 2015). Nurses with this trait can easily be given to complaining of workload, and it will be very difficult for such nurse to carry out her work effectively in the hospitals. All these traits mentioned have great implication for nurse's job performance in their various hospitals.

Several studies have examined the relationship between personality traits and job performance of nurses. Tan, Lim and Hassan (2021) carried out a study to explore the relationship between personality traits and organizational commitment. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The study sampled 200 nurses from public hospitals in Ontario. They found out neuroticism had a positive relationship with continuance commitment in the organization; extraversion had positive relationship with affective commitment and normative commitment but negative relationship with continuance commitment. Openness to experience was found to have a negative relationship with continuance commitment. However, agreeableness had a positive relationship with normative commitment while conscientiousness had a positive relationship with affective and continuance commitment. Austin and Boyd, (2018) meta-analysis concerning relationships between personality traits and various facets of nurses job performance found Agreeableness ($r = .17$), two facets of Conscientiousness (Achievement; $r = .14$ and Dependability; $r = .17$), and Emotional Stability ($r = .13$) to be related to teamwork. Meanwhile, Acaray and Yildirim (2017) concluded in a Meta-analysis that conscientiousness has positive relationship with job performance. Researches on Extraversion personality trait also reveal that it affects job performance positively as well the main feature of extraversion as sociable, assertiveness and activeness.

In a study by Emecheta, Awa and Ukoha (2016) investigated the relationship between personality characteristics and affective

organisation commitment among Bank employees in Nigeria. The study sample consisted of 210 respondents from ten 10 purposively selected bank branches in Port Harcourt. The study revealed that a positive and significant relationship exist between the five personality dimensions and affective organisation commitment. Research conducted by Bing and Lounsbury (2019) examined the impact of openness on job performance within Japanese manufacturing companies based in the United States. A questionnaire was used to elicit data from a sample of 111 respondents. Data was analyzed using the descriptive statistics. The result concluded that extraversion dimension can be valid predictor in social-related works such as sales persons and managerial jobs.

Ajayi, Shiyabade, Ajayi, Olodude and Olowoporoku (2017) examined the influence of personality traits, and work commitment on Job performance of public secondary school teachers in Oyo South Senatorial District of Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The sample for this study consisted of 15 principals, 75 HODs and 300 class teachers in the senatorial district. Frequency counts, simple percentages, chi-square and one-way ANOVA statistics were employed to analyze the data.

The results revealed that 15.7%, 67.9% and 16.4% of public secondary school teachers in the senatorial district demonstrated low, moderate and high levels of job performance respectively. Also, 72.1% of the teachers had a moderate level of work commitment, 1.7% had a high level while 11.7% had a low level of work commitment. The results further showed that there was no significant influence of personality traits on teacher's job performance ($\chi^2 = 6.730$, $df = 8$, $p = 566$). A study conducted by Barrick *et al.* (2017) examined the relationship between personality traits and job performance in 100 technology professionals from the USA. The study found that conscientiousness and

emotional stability were strong indicators of job performance.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigerian public hospitals, notable variations exist in nurses' job performance, with some nurses outperforming others. This disparity may stem from factors such as resource scarcity, high patient volume, diverse health needs, or the personality traits of individual nurses (Nantsupawat, 2021). While researchers have debated whether job performance is determined more by personality traits or environmental factors (Alloush, 2022), the role of personality traits is particularly critical in nursing because nurses are directly responsible for patient care and life outcomes. Studies have shown that personality traits effective in one context may be ineffective in another (Judge & Zapata, 2015), underscoring the need for context-specific investigation.

Several studies have established a connection between personality traits and job performance across various professions (Alloush, 2022; Holman & Hughes, 2021). However, the nursing profession presents unique challenges—emotional labor, shift work, patient diversity, and high-stakes decision-making—that require dedicated examination, especially within public hospitals. Public hospitals in Nigeria operate under resource constraints, high patient volumes, limited staffing, and complex healthcare needs, making the understanding of personality–performance linkages essential for recruitment, training, and human resource management.

Although existing research has explored personality and job performance in healthcare settings, a significant gap remains regarding the specific context of public hospitals in Edo State, Nigeria. Factors such as financial limitations, bureaucratic processes, and local patient demographics may uniquely moderate the relationship between personality traits and job

performance. Furthermore, findings from private hospitals or other countries may not generalize to this setting due to differences in healthcare systems and organizational cultures.

Therefore, despite prior recommendations from studies suggesting that nurses' personality traits can enhance job performance, the fundamental question remains unresolved in this context: Do nurses' personality traits significantly predict their job performance in public hospitals in Edo State?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate personality traits as predictors of job performance among nurses in public hospitals in Edo State of Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to examine the:

- a) relationship between openness to experience and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State;
- b) relationship between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State;
- c) relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State;
- d) relationship between agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State;
- e) relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State.

Hypotheses of the Study

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in this study

- 1) There is no significant relationship between openness to experience and

- job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State
- 2) There is no significant relationship between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State
 - 3) There is no significant relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State
 - 4) There is no significant relationship between agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State
 - 5) There is no significant relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State

Research Method

This study adopted the correlational research design. Kendra Cherry and Emily Swaim (2023) defined correlational research design as the relationship between two or more variables. This design is considered appropriate because the researcher sought to examine the relationship between nurses' personality traits (Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism and Openness to Experience) and their job performance in public hospitals in Edo State.

The population of this study consists of all nurses with a total population of 320 in hospitals owned by the Edo state government. This was made up of all the nurses in the thirty-one (31) state-owned hospitals, located in the eighteen (18) local government areas of Edo State. As at October, 2025, the total population of nurses in these public hospitals. A total of 222 nurses were selected through a multistage stratified random sampling technique. First, 31 public hospitals were chosen from the three senatorial districts of the state using systematic random sampling. Then, a purposive (deliberate) method was applied to select nurses from these hospitals out of the

entire 320 nurses. Nurses from Oredo LGA's Central Hospital were sampled at 40% due to their larger size, while all nurses in the remaining hospitals were included. This method ensured a fair representation of the nursing population across the state.

The study employed a structured questionnaire titled "Personality Traits and Nurses Performance Questionnaire (PTJPNQ)" to measure two key variables: nurses' personality traits and their job performance. The instrument was adapted from John and Srivastava's (1999) Big Five personality framework and was divided into three sections. Section B assessed nurses' personality traits using 25 items that represented the five major domains: Extraversion, Agreeableness, Conscientiousness, Neuroticism, and Openness to Experience. All items were rated on a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. Section C evaluated job performance and was adapted from Schwirian's (1978) Six Dimension Scale of Nurses Job Performance (SDSNJP). To suit the workload of practicing nurses, 20 items were selected, 10 focusing on patient-related tasks and 10 on non-patient-related duties.

In order to ascertain the validity of the instruments, the researcher adopted the content and construct validity technique. The instrument was presented to the experts in the Department of Guidance and Counselling, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma for critical examination of its contents. These experts ensured that questions asked were relevant to the topic under study. Reliability was tested using a test-retest method, with all traits showing scores above 0.70, indicating strong consistency.

The researcher, with the help of two trained assistants, distributed the questionnaires in the selected hospitals over three weeks. A total of 222 completed responses were collected for analysis which recorded 100%

of return rate of 222 questionnaire administered. To analyze the data, Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the relationships

between individual personality traits and job performance. The results were evaluated based on statistical significance using a p-value threshold of 0.05.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between openness to experience

and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Table 1: Summary of Pearson r on mean response on the relationship between openness to experience and job performance

Variable	N	Mean	SD	d.f	Correlation Index (x)	P-value	Decision
Openness	51	2.57	.861				Null hypothesis
Job performance	51	2.39	.594	49	.701**	0.001	rejected (p<0.05)

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation statistics presented in Table 1 showed that the mean (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation core (SD) of the respondents (N = 51) where 2.57 and 0.861 for the openness to experience and 2.39 and 0.594 for the nurses job performance respectively. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.701 was significant (p<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between openness to

experience and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state was rejected. This implies that a strong and positive relationship exist between openness to experience and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state

Table 2: Summary of Pearson R on mean response of the relationship between conscientiousness and job performance

Variable	N	Mean	SD	d.f	Correlation Index (x)	P-value	Decision
Conscientiousness	50	2.48	.755				Null hypothesis
Job performance	50	2.29	.438	48	.683**	0.002	rejected (p<0.05)

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation statistics presented in Table 1 showed that the mean (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation core (SD) of the respondents (N = 50) where 2.48 and 0.755 for conscientiousness and 2.29 and 0.438 for the nurses job performance respectively. The

Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.683 was significant (p<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state was

rejected. This implies that a moderate and positive relationship exist between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State

Table 3: Summary of Pearson-r on mean response of relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state

Variable	N	Mean	SD	d.f	Correlation Index (x)	P-value	Decision
Extroversion	52	2.60	.749	50	.703**	0.001	Null hypothesis rejected (p<0.05)
Job performance	52	2,36	.448				

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation statistics presented in Table 1 showed that the mean (\bar{X}) and the standard deviation core (SD) of the respondents (N = 52) where 2.60 and 0.749 for the extroversion and 2.36 and 0.448 for the nurses job performance respectively. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.703 was significant (p<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses

in public hospitals in Edo state was rejected. This implies that a strong and positive relationship exist between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State

Table 4: summary of Pearson-r on mean response of the relationship between Agreeableness and Job Performance of Nurses

Variable	N	Mean	SD	d.f	Correlation Index (r)	P-value	Decision
Agreeableness	51	2.53	.781	49	.689**	0.002	Null hypothesis rejected (p<0.05)
Job performance	51	2,37	.536				

****.** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The correlation statistics presented in Table 1 showed that the mean (X) and the standard deviation core (SD) of the respondents (N = 51) where 2.53 and 0.781 for agreeableness and 2.37 and 0.536 for the nurses job performance respectively. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.689 was significant (p<0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between agreeableness and job performance of nurses

in public hospitals in Edo state was rejected. This implies that a moderate positive relationship exist between agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public-hospitals in Edo state.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Table 5: Summary of Pearson-r on mean response of the relationship between neuroticism and job performance

Variable	N	Mean	SD	d.f	Correlation Index (r)	P-value	Decision
Neuroticism	18	2.28	.406				Null hypothesis
Job performance	18	2.11	.216	16	-.039*	0.278	retained (p>0.05)

****.** *Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).*

The correlation statistics presented in Table 5 showed that the mean (X) and the standard deviation core (SD) of the respondents (N = 18) where 2.28 and .406 for neuroticism and 2.11 and .216 for the nurses job performance respectively. The Pearson correlation coefficient of -.039 was insignificant (p>0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state was retained. This implies that a negative and insignificant relationship exist between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State.

Discussion

The result showed that there was a strong positive relationship between openness to experience and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State. This positive correlation implies that as levels of openness to experience increase among nurses, their job performance tends to improve as well. This finding aligns with the notion that individuals who are more open to new experiences may be more adaptable, innovative, and willing to engage in continuous learning, all of which are traits that can positively influence job performance. This agreed with the study of Deniz et al. (2020) found that nurses with higher levels of openness to experience demonstrated superior job performance, characterized by greater patient satisfaction and lower rates of medical errors. Austin and

Boyd, (2018) synthesized findings from multiple studies across different industries and professions, concluding that openness to experience consistently predicts higher levels of job performance.

The result showed that there was a moderate positive relationship between conscientiousness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. This shows the importance of conscientiousness as a predictor of job performance among nurses. It means that nurses who exhibit traits such as diligence, responsibility, and attention to detail may be more likely to deliver higher-quality patient care and meet organizational objectives effectively. This finding aligned with Sayyed, Mohamad and Sayyed (2017) found a positive correlation between conscientiousness and job performance. Their research supported the notion that conscientious individuals are more likely to exhibit behaviour that enhance effective job performance, such as thoroughness and reliability. Erdenk and Altuntaş (2017) also affirmed a positive association between conscientiousness and job performance. Their findings emphasized the role of conscientiousness in facilitating goal-directed behaviour and achievement in workplace.

The result showed that there was a strong positive significant relationship between extroversion and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. The analysis indicates a significant positive correlation between extroversion and job

performance. This suggests that there indeed exists a significant relationship between these variables among nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. This also underscores the importance of considering personality traits, such as extroversion, in the context of job performance among nurses. Nurses who exhibit higher levels of extroversion may possess qualities such as sociability, assertiveness, and enthusiasm, which could positively influence their job performance. This correlate with Emecheta, Awa and Ukoha (2016) *they* found a positive correlation between extroversion and job performance. Their research highlighted the role of extroverted traits, such as effective communication and interpersonal skills, in facilitating job performance outcomes among nurses. Syed, Saeed, and Farrukh, (2015) also affirmed a positive association between extroversion and job performance. Their findings emphasized the contribution of extroverted traits to team dynamics, leadership effectiveness, and overall job satisfaction.

The result showed that there was a moderate positive relationship between agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. This indicates that there indeed exists a significant relationship between these variables among nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. This shows the relevance of agreeableness as a predictor of job performance among nurses. Nurses who exhibit higher levels of agreeableness may possess qualities such as cooperativeness, empathy, and teamwork, which can positively influence their interactions with colleagues, patients, and overall organizational effectiveness. This finding is in agreement with the study of Chiaburu et al (2016) who found a positive correlation between agreeableness and job performance. Their research highlighted the role of agreeable traits in promoting effective communication, collaboration, and patient-centered care delivery. Cherry, (2019) also found a positive association between agreeableness and job performance. Their

findings emphasized the importance of agreeable traits in fostering interpersonal relationships and organizational citizenship behaviour.

The result showed that there was weak and negative relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state. This could be as a result of the impact of neuroticism, characterized by traits such as anxiety, worry, and emotional instability on job performance among nurses. Hence, nurses with higher levels of neuroticism may experience heightened stress levels, impacting their ability to perform effectively in their roles. This finding is consistent with several recent studies in the field. For instance, a study by Bruk-Lee, Khoury, Nixon, Goh, and Spector (2019) found that neuroticism was not a significant predictor of job performance among healthcare workers, highlighting the complex interplay of various personality traits in predicting job outcomes.

Conclusion

The role of personality traits in predicting job performance among nurses in public hospitals in Edo state cannot be undermined. Based on findings, it is concluded that there is a positive relationship between openness to experience, conscientiousness, extroversion and agreeableness and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo State. However, there was a weak and negative (inverse) relationship between neuroticism and job performance of nurses in public hospitals in Edo state.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) There should be professional development programmes tailored to enhance nurses' openness to new ideas and practices, fostering a culture of innovation and adaptability within the workplace.
- 2) There should be clear guidelines and protocols established to promote conscientious behaviour among

nursing staff, emphasizing the importance of reliability and accountability in delivering high-quality patient care.

- 3) There should be opportunities for nurses to develop and refine their interpersonal skills through communication training and teamwork exercises, fostering an environment that values collaboration and effective communication.
- 4) There is need to focus on promoting a supportive and respectful work culture where agreeable behaviour is recognized and encouraged, leading to improved teamwork and patient outcomes.
- 5) There should be resources and support systems in place to help male nurses manage stress and maintain emotional well-being, ensuring that job-related stressors do not negatively impact performance and patient care.

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